

Gender Stereotypes in Chhota Bheem: Impact on Children's Perceptions and Socialization

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Abstract

This study explores how gender stereotypes in Chhota Bheem affect children's perceptions, socialization, and attitudes by analyzing visual and auditory depictions of gender roles. It aims to contribute to understanding the broader impact of gender representations in children's media, emphasizing gender disparities and the potential restriction of women characters in selected episodes.

Keywords: gender stereotypes, child psychology, animated media, Chhota Bheem, societal attitudes.

“See no gender, hear no gender, speak no gender - see only human, hear only human, speak only human.” - Abhijit Naskar, See No Gender

Childhood memories frequently occupy a unique and cherished space, with moments linked to cartoons standing out among these recollections. Beyond mere entertainment during this developmental period, animated shows hold a significant role as influential educational resources for children. Therefore, delving into the effects of cartoons on a child's psychology and behaviour becomes essential. According to Robinson and Shaw (2008) (cited in “Cartoons' Impact on Children”), cartoons play a pivotal role in aiding young children in effortlessly grasping complex ideas. They contribute to the development of a child's working memory, act as a source of stimulation, and enhance their visual learning style. In the early phases of life, children are highly receptive to external influences. They are modelled according to the surrounding setting in which they reside. They have fun through the cartoon program but it can affect them both positively and negatively. The impact of cartoons on a child's behaviour can sometimes surpass the influence of their family or immediate surroundings. This is because a child's environment is typically confined, whereas cartoons transport them on extensive journeys into the realms of both reality and imagination.

Cartoons, in this sense, serve as an expansive gateway for a child's cognitive development, offering exposure to a multitude of ideas and scenarios. Unlike the limited scope of a child's immediate environment, cartoons provide a broader canvas that can shape a child's perception of the world. Therefore, understanding the profound influence of cartoons on a child's psychological and behavioural development is essential for recognizing the role they play in shaping the early stages of cognitive growth.

It is crucial for parents to grasp that children perceive the world through a unique lens, and fictional narratives serve as indispensable tools in nurturing a positive understanding of life's intricate dynamics. Fairy tales, commonly the foundation of cartoons, are rich in diverse symbols that contribute significantly to the cognitive and moral development of children. According to acclaimed child psychology expert Maurizio Brassini, the narratives and the dichotomy between good and evil portrayed in cartoons exert a substantial influence on a child's personality.

However, the impact hinges on the nature of the cartoons a child engages with; they hold the potential to instil virtuous values and ethics or, conversely, foster a propensity towards violence, irritability, and the endorsement of negative habits and deleterious behaviours. Therefore, the content of these animated stories plays a pivotal role in shaping a child's character, either providing a reservoir of constructive ideals or presenting a worrisome array of detrimental influences on a proverbial silver platter.

The influence of certain forms of media on children's minds is inevitable, particularly given the entertainment-focused nature of these mediums. While cartoon episodes captivate young audiences visually, they also wield a crucial role in shaping social perspectives. Characters depicted in these cartoons often exemplify specific behaviours and qualities that young minds internalize and aspire to emulate in their future lives. This phenomenon is evident in the expectations that children develop concerning idealized gender roles and behaviours. In today's world of nuclear family setting, electronic media assumes a key role in reshaping the traditional oral narratives of fairy tales. Mythical tales featuring superheroes have gained immense popularity within the television industry. These digital renditions of folktales serve a dual purpose: they preserve conventional values and cultural elements for future generations, while simultaneously portraying television as an omnipresent force in the daily lives of children. This depiction contributes to the formation of ideas about gender roles and among

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children, as exemplified by the representation of gender identities in cartoon shows. As noted by Baker, cartoon programs often revolve around a superhero character who embarks on missions, confronts adversaries, and makes challenging decisions. Male superheroes are typically depicted as muscular, while their female counterparts are portrayed with average body types, with females being deemed more attractive in comparison to males (38).

The impact of cartoons, delivered through both visual and auditory mediums, is a powerful and influential form of communication. Characters like Chutki and Indumati in the *Chota Bheem* series exemplify this influence. However, a concerning aspect arises when examining the presence of gender bias in these cartoons, perpetuated by stereotypical mindsets. Such biases assign specific roles to genders, portraying girls as inherently weak and confined to domestic tasks, while positioning males as strong and superior. This gender disparity not only reflects an ingrained inferiority associated with female characters but also underscores a perpetuation of traditional gender roles. The creation of such gender disparities in cartoon series reflects a deeply rooted bias inherited from predecessors and cultural norms.

Chotta Bheem stands out as an immensely popular cartoon series among Indian children, unfolding the tales of a young boy in the enchanting setting of Dholakpur. The primary characters, including Bheem, Chutki, Kaalia, Indumati, Raju, Jaggu, Dholu, and Bholu, collectively navigate the narrative landscape. Bheem, as the unequivocal protagonist, consistently emerges as the saviour of his friends, adept at resolving various challenges that unfold throughout the storyline.

Bheem, renowned for his formidable strength and benevolent nature, draws inspiration from a character in the Mahabharata, a fact evident in his very name which conveys power and might. However, this formidable portrayal of Bheem serves to accentuate the gender disparity within the cartoon, especially in relation to his counterpart, Chutki, who is portrayed as a fragile and feeble girl. This stark contrast underscores the prevailing gender dynamics embedded in the narrative.

Children formulate notions of gender stereotypes through their engagement with cartoons, as they engage in fantasies about the characters and emulate them in various ways. This leads to the recognition that the imposition of gender roles is a societal ailment perpetuated by the media, with its roots firmly embedded in the minds of young children who navigate

between the realms of fantasy and reality. However, societal focus on issues of masculinity remains insufficient:

To alter our cultural perceptions of dominant masculinity and the hierarchical systems intertwined with it, the initial step involves reconceptualizing masculinity as a gender. This entails highlighting its socially constructed and evolving nature, thereby providing spaces for children to perceive themselves as catalysts for change (Wannamaker 148).

In the realm of cartoons, a distinct hierarchy of characters emerges, with the dominant and solver. This hegemonic male figure, exemplified by Bheem, occupying the role of protagonist and problem portrayal reinforces stereotypical notions of masculinity, where the idealized male character boasts muscularity, handsomeness, and other culturally predefined features. Conversely, characters like Dholu and Bholu are depicted as lacking in qualities, often portrayed as submissive and, at times, powerless. Chutki and Indumati's contributions to conflict resolution are predominantly advisory in nature, further reinforcing traditional gender roles. Their attempts to resolve conflicts are presented in a comical manner, highlighting their inadequacies. It's important to note that such portrayals can contribute to the reinforcement of gender stereotypes, influencing the perceptions and expectations of young viewers. Media has a significant impact on shaping societal attitudes, and representations like these may inadvertently contribute to the normalization of certain gender dynamics. It's essential for media creators to be mindful of the messages they convey and strive for more diverse and empowering portrayals of characters, irrespective of gender.

The series showcases a notable disparity in character representation, with only three female characters compared to the abundant presence of five or more male characters. This unequal distribution implies a diminished significance assigned to female characters, as opposed to the ample space afforded to exploring masculinity. Judith Butler's theory of performativity offers a valuable lens through which to critically examine gender stereotypes in Chhota Bheem. According to Butler, gender is not an inherent or fixed trait but is constructed through repetitive performances of societal norms and expectations. Individuals "do" gender through their actions, and these performances contribute to the perpetuation of gender norms.

In the context of Chhota Bheem, traditional gender stereotypes are evident in the way characters like Chutki are portrayed. Chutki often conforms to stereotypical feminine traits, playing a submissive and supportive role to the male protagonist, Chhota Bheem. Her character's actions and expressions align with conventional expectations of femininity, reinforcing the idea that certain behaviours are inherently associated with being female.

By adhering to these gender stereotypes, the show may unintentionally contribute to the normalization and reinforcement of traditional gender roles among its young audience. The repetition of these gendered performances in media can shape children's understanding of what is considered "normal" behaviour for boys and girls, limiting the range of possibilities for their own self-expression. To challenge these stereotypes, creators could introduce more diverse and non-conforming gender representations, allowing for a broader range of performances that go beyond traditional expectations. This could contribute to a more inclusive and empowering portrayal of gender in children's media.

The portrayal of Chutki in Chhota Bheem as a submissive character can be observed through the character's behaviour and interactions within the show. Chutki's depiction aligns with traditional gender roles, where she often assumes a more passive nature contrast to the assertive and adventurous nature of the male protagonist, Chhota Bheem. Chutki is frequently shown in situations where she relies on Chhota Bheem for protection or assistance, reinforcing a stereotypical gender dynamic. This portrayal reinforces traditional gender norms, suggesting that female characters are dependent on male counterparts and are more inclined toward domestic or supportive roles.

Chutki's character further aligns with traditional Indian societal norms, reflecting the contentment of Indian wives with their husbands' triumphs. Engaged primarily in domestic responsibilities due to the absence of her mother, Chutki symbolizes the contentment derived from Bheem's victories and the fulfilment found in attending to household chores. These facets of Chutki's character, as observed in the selected episode, serve as nuanced reflections of prevailing societal norms and expectations.

Bheem epitomizes highly masculine characteristics, possessing a broad-shouldered physique with six-pack abs, courage, power, and intelligence. The cartoon's title song reinforces an image of an assertive, action-oriented, and formidable male figure through the

character of Bheem: “Bheem ki shakti dhoom machaye, samne koi tik na paye... Dushman bach ke na jaye, Bheem shakti aisi dikhaye” (Bheem’s physical power is so formidable that nobody can stand in front of him... enemies cannot escape from his grip because Bheem is so powerful).(Chilaka, Chotta Bheem)

Throughout the episodes, Bheem consistently appears as a saviour, akin to the heroes from traditional fairy tales. Female characters in the cartoon, such as Chutki, follow Bheem’s lead, while Princess Indumati consistently seeks Bheem’s assistance for protection. Bheem is positioned as the epitome of perfection within the group, with even King Indravarman turning to him for help in saving Dholakpur. The cartoon conveys the notion that the male protagonist, Bheem, bears a significant responsibility on his shoulders. As an ideal man, he is expected to prioritize the well-being of others, often requiring personal sacrifices. Bheem, renowned for his robust strength and compassionate nature, draws inspiration from a character in the Mahabharata, as evident in his name, signifying power and might. However, this formidable depiction of Bheem serves to highlight the gender disparity ingrained in the cartoon, notably concerning his counterpart, Chutki, portrayed as delicate and vulnerable. This glaring dichotomy underscores the prevalent gender dynamics woven into the storyline.

In various episodes, Chutki is depicted as harboring feelings for Bheem, evidenced by her jealousy when he interacts with other girls. Chutki’s mother, who crafts ladoos - a source of strength for Bheem, further emphasizes the traditional gender roles assigned to female characters. Both Chutki and Indumati are consistently portrayed in skirts and blouses, with long hair, adhering to a predetermined construct that restricts their character development. The cultural portrayal of women as dependent, passive, submissive, and incompetent is a recurring theme, perpetuating stereotypes of femininity in a younger context. In her article titled “One Is Not Born a Woman”, Monique Wittig questions: “The building of concepts that we accept as natural about gender and makes an explanation about what we naturalize as human beings. By admitting that there is a ‘natural’ division between women and men, we naturalize history, we assume that ‘men’ and ‘women’ have always existed and will always exist. Not only do we naturalize history, but also consequently we naturalize the social phenomena which express our oppression, making change impossible” (Wittig, “One Is Not Born a Woman”).

In each adventurous episode, Chutki’s impact is not merely indirect; rather, she bears a share of the responsibility for their collective victories. She occupies a prominent space within

the group, standing as the second-in-command after Bheem himself. This elevated position is not merely symbolic; it is substantiated by her active participation in activities traditionally associated with the male domain, such as archery and wrestling competitions (episode, Sumo Battle Zone). These domains, acknowledged for their historical male-centric nature, underscore Chutki's remarkable role in transcending gender stereotypes within the group dynamics. Her involvement challenges preconceived notions and establishes her as a dynamic and indispensable force in the collective successes of Bheem's team.

Chutki assumes a secondary place within the narrative, with Raju standing out as the most physically adept companion in the group. Despite her secondary position, Chutki's character is characterized by a nature that embodies praise, kindness, and generosity towards not only Bheem but also others in the group. Occasionally showcasing intelligence, her capabilities often go unrecognized in the context of a male-dominated and patriarchal domain.

Interestingly, each character in the series possesses a distinct name, even down to the monkey, Jaggu. However, Chutki's name itself, which translates to "tiny" or "small", seems to relegate her to an unrecognizable and seemingly insignificant space. This nomenclature subtly reinforces the notion of her character being perceived as diminutive and perhaps overlooked in the overarching narrative.

In a special episode dedicated to Mother's Day, Chutki endeavours to create a memorable day for her mother. In this particular narrative arc, she takes it upon herself to bring flowers and shoulder the responsibility of all household chores, providing her mother with a well-deserved break. This gesture not only reflects Chutki's inherent kindness but also serves to showcase her determination to create meaningful moments for her family. Despite her secondary role, such instances illuminate Chutki's character as one with depth, resilience, and a commitment to nurturing familial bonds.

In the highlighted episode, Bheem and his group members frequently step in to assist and undertake the necessary physical tasks. This depiction suggests a portrayal of Chutki as incapable of managing her own responsibilities. She engages in household chores, such as cleaning the house and preparing ladoos for her mother's sweet stall, with the assistance of others to fulfil her duties for the day. This portrayal tends to characterize her as unskilled and reliant on her friends, particularly in physical tasks.

Another noteworthy episode is the one where Chutki becomes the victim of a kidnapping, illustrating her as a helpless object dependent on Bheem for her rescue. Bheem, in contrast, is presented as possessing the knowledge and skills to adeptly resolve the predicament. These two episodes collectively contribute to a narrative that may influence children to believe in the inherent incompetence of women, reinforcing stereotypes embedded in cultural and ancestral knowledge.

Repeated instances across various episodes highlight the limited screen time allocated to Chutki, often confined to two brief shots within a mere ten seconds. This temporal constraint deliberately marginalizes her character, perpetuating a pattern of minimized representation. In the chosen cartoon episode, Chutki's portrayal is marked by confined space, inefficiency, and passivity. The constructed space for female characters within the series appears to conform to certain stereotypes, emphasizing Bheem's efficiency and active engagement in various roles. This stark contrast reinforces societal norms that have the potential to shape children's perceptions regarding gender roles and capabilities.

The deliberate marginalization of Chutki's character raises concerns about the impact on young viewers, as they may internalize these gendered representations. The brevity of her screen time contributes to an overall narrative that assigns limited agency and significance to female characters, contrasting with the robust portrayal of the male protagonist, Bheem.

In considering the words of Sally Armstrong, emphasizing the power of the current generation to bring about change, it becomes imperative to critically evaluate the messages conveyed by children's media. The juxtaposition of Chutki's limited presence with the assertion of power and change highlights the need for a more inclusive and diverse representation of gender roles in children's programming.

It is essential to recognize and address these issues to promote a more inclusive and unbiased representation in children's media. "We cannot measure what Children learn from stories and books. Any particular word or image could strike them in a way that can never be expressed. Rather than focusing on one particular moral Children should be encouraged to read passionately, with an open mind" (The Postwoman and Other Stories). Priyadarshini's words serve as a concluding statement, highlighting the imperative of nurturing a holistic approach to children's literature. Instead of concentrating solely on singular morals, there is a call for

children to embrace passionate reading with open minds, enabling stories to influence them in profound and nuanced ways. This approach not only cultivates a broader understanding of the world but also fosters critical thinking that extends beyond rigid and prescriptive narratives.

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